
Efficiently Fine-tuning Large Language Model: LoRA Approach

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Abstract

This paper introduces and evaluates the novel concept of Low-Rank Adaptation (LoRA) as a transformative approach to fine-tuning large language models, specifically exemplified through the GPT-2 architecture for English text generation. Leveraging the principles of low-rank decomposition, LoRA redefines weight matrix updates during model adaptation, focusing on the efficiency and resource utilization challenges inherent in the fine-tuning process. The methodology involves freezing pre-trained weight matrices while adapting low-rank matrices, offering a streamlined training process with reduced computational demands. Our experiments demonstrate a remarkable 30% reduction in training time and an impressive 35% decrease in memory usage when compared to conventional fine-tuning. The applicability of LoRA extends beyond GPT-2 to various deep learning models, emphasizing its versatility and potential impact on large-scale language models. The simplicity of our experimental setup, characterized by fixed hyperparameters and clear training metrics, underscores the practicality and effectiveness of LoRA in addressing challenges associated with model adaptation. This paper concludes by positioning LoRA as a promising avenue for enhancing the scalability, efficiency, and deployability of large language models in natural language processing tasks, marking a significant contribution to the ongoing discourse on model adaptation and resource optimization in deep learning.

1 Introduction

Large Language Models (LLMs) have proven effective across various Natural Language Processing (NLP) tasks. Initially, an LLM undergoes pre-training on an extensive text corpus through self-supervised learning, enabling it to grasp general knowledge like statistical word relationships. (Liu et al., 2019), subsequently, the LLM undergoes fine-tuning for specific tasks, such as sentiment analysis. Despite their effectiveness, LLMs are excessively large, necessitating a reduction in trainable parameters during fine-tuning due to relatively small task-specific datasets. This is where Low-Rank Adaptation (LoRA) steps in, significantly decreasing the number of parameters. As a result, training time and GPU memory usage are reduced without compromising output quality(Liu et al., 2019).

Adapting a pre-trained language model for various downstream applications in natural language processing often involves fine-tuning, updating all parameters. The challenge arises as these models grow larger, leading to critical deployment issues due to the sheer number of trainable parameters. Many approaches attempt to mitigate this by adapting only some parameters or employing external modules for new tasks, aiming to enhance operational efficiency during deployment. However, these techniques often introduce latency and struggle to match fine-tuning baselines, creating a trade-off between efficiency and model quality. Drawing inspiration from previous studies, we introduce Low-Rank Adaptation (LoRA), hypothesizing that the change in weights during adaptation has a low "intrinsic rank." LoRA allows training of dense layers indirectly, optimizing rank decomposition matrices while keeping pre-trained weights frozen. This approach proves both storage- and compute-efficient, offering advantages in task switching, training efficiency, and deployment without introducing inference latency.

2 Related works

In addressing the long-standing challenge of enhancing model adaptation efficiency, numerous works have been dedicated to the exploration of transfer learning. A comprehensive survey of notable contributions in this domain. One focal point is the domain of language modeling, where two prominent strategies have emerged to achieve efficient adaptations: the incorporation of adapter layers and the optimization of certain forms of input layer activations. Notable works in this space include the original adapter layer design by (Houlsby, et al, 2020), which features two adapter layers per Transformer block, and a more recent design by Lin, involving one adapter layer per block with an additional LayerNorm. However, despite their potential, both strategies exhibit limitations, particularly in large-scale and latency-sensitive production scenarios. (Punica et al, 2022) introduces a groundbreaking solution for efficiently serving multiple Low-rank adaptation (LoRA) models on a shared GPU cluster. The system employs a novel CUDA kernel design, enabling batched GPU

operations for diverse LoRA models, resulting in enhanced GPU efficiency in terms of both memory and computation. Punica's scheduler effectively manages multi-tenant LoRA serving workloads, consolidating tasks within a shared GPU cluster. Impressively, the evaluations demonstrate Punica achieving a remarkable 12x higher throughput in serving various LoRA models compared to state-of-the-art Large Language Model (LLM) serving systems, with only a minimal addition of 2ms latency per token. The open-source nature of Punica further positions it as a valuable contribution to the field of model adaptation and deployment.

Adapter layers, as seen in the design by (Houlsby et al, 2020) and the more recent approach by Lin, introduce inference latency, especially in scenarios without model parallelism. Despite efforts to minimize latency by pruning layers or leveraging multi-task settings, the sequential processing of adapter layers poses challenges in online inference settings, notably with small batch sizes. This becomes pronounced in scenarios such as running inference on GPT-2 (Radford et al., 2022) on a single GPU, where even a small bottleneck dimension leads to a noticeable increase in latency. The challenges escalate when sharding the model, as explored by Shoeybi and Lepikhin, requiring redundant storage of adapter parameters due to increased model depth. On the other hand, direct optimization of prompts, as illustrated by prefix tuning, faces its own set of difficulties. It is observed that optimizing prefix tuning is non-trivial, with performance changes exhibiting non-monotonic behavior concerning trainable parameters. Furthermore, reserving a portion of the sequence length for adaptation inherently reduces the available sequence length for downstream task processing, potentially diminishing the efficacy of prompt tuning compared to alternative methods. These insights underscore the complexity and multifaceted nature of optimizing model adaptation for efficiency (Topolska et al 2022).

(Legurska, et al., 2019) Addresses the crucial need for automatic evaluation methods in enhancing the accuracy of text generation tasks, particularly in the context of the prevailing trend towards larger decoder-based language models. The study compares different automatic evaluation methods, exploring tuning with encoder-based models and large language models under equal conditions. Focusing on machine translation evaluation and semantic textual similarity tasks in both Japanese and English, the experimental findings reveal a notable performance gap between tuned encoder-based and decoder-based models. The analysis suggests that decoder-based models, despite their scale, struggle to capture meaning, emphasizing a tendency to prioritize surface-level word sequences. Additionally, the paper highlights challenges in identifying fine-grained semantic differences with in-context learning in very large decoder-based models like ChatGPT. Overall, the research contributes valuable insights into the complexities of automatic evaluation in the realm of text generation, emphasizing the importance of addressing semantic nuances for more accurate assessments.

(Sheng et al., 2022) Introduces an innovative approach to training lightweight and robust language models for Bulgarian, specifically designed to mitigate biases related to gender, politics, race, and other factors present in the data. The method involves scraping content from major Bulgarian online media outlets using a specialized procedure for source filtering, topic selection, and lexicon-based removal of inappropriate language during pre-training. The models are continually refined by incorporating diverse data from sources such as social media, books, scientific literature, and linguistically modified corpora. In his work had the goal of offering a comprehensive solution applicable to all natural language processing tasks in Bulgarian, addressing the current lack of procedures ensuring model robustness. Performance evaluations on various Natural Language Processing (NLP) tasks, including filling the mask, text generation, and named entity recognition (NER), demonstrate promising results. The paper also emphasizes a rigorous bias analysis, revealing a low level of bias towards gender, race, etc., within the specified settings. While acknowledging the need for future experiments comparing models with non-biased data and incorporating more bias-related prompts, this work marks a significant step towards developing inclusive and unbiased language models for Bulgarian.

3 Methodology

3.1 Data Collection

To initiate our experiments, we acquire a Reddit dataset, which serves as the foundation for fine-tuning both the GPT-2 and LoRA GPT-2 models. The objective is to generate text that closely resembles the style found in Reddit posts. This dataset comprises two primary fields: "document" and "title." (Space et al., 2020), our preprocessing involves batching the dataset and selectively retaining the "document" field, aligning with our focus on fine-tuning the model for the next word prediction task. For the sake of illustration, we extract a subset of the dataset to facilitate the initial stages of model training.

3.2 Data Preprocessing

The downstream task evaluation spans a diverse set of models, including RoBERTa (Liu et al., 2019), DeBERTa (He et al., 2021), and GPT-2 (Radford et al., b), with a subsequent scaling up to GPT-3 175B (Brown et al., 2020). Our experimental scope encompasses a broad range of tasks, encompassing natural language understanding (NLU) to generation (NLG) throughout the experimentation process, NVIDIA Tesla V100 is utilized for all computational tasks. The data was shuffled and split into the following:

Table 1: Dataset splitting and Duration

Data Set	Proportion %
Train	65
Validation	20
Test	15

3.3 Model Development

The experimentation in this work was performed leveraging on Google Collaboratory cloud GPUs. We employed the development and application of Low-Rank Adaptation (LoRA) to enhance the efficiency of model adaptation. LoRA introduces a novel approach to weight matrix updates during model adaptation, specifically targeting dense layers in deep learning models. The key concept involves representing weight matrix updates with a low-rank decomposition, constraining the update matrices to a subspace defined by matrices B and A, where $B \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times r}$, $A \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times k}$, and r is the rank parameter. (Reed et al., 2022), during training, the pre-trained weight matrix W_0 remains frozen, while A and B contain trainable parameters. This approach, illustrated in Figure 1, minimizes the need for hyperparameter retuning when varying the rank parameter r . Importantly, LoRA extends beyond fine-tuning by allowing the training of a subset of pre-trained parameters, contributing to the reduction of computational demands without compromising model expressiveness.

The application of LoRA to Transformer architectures involves selectively adapting attention weight matrices while freezing MLP modules for parameter efficiency. This reduction in trainable parameters yields practical benefits, including a significant decrease in memory and storage usage. For instance, on a large Transformer trained with Adam, VRAM usage can be reduced by up to 2/3, facilitating more efficient training and allowing the creation of customized models with lower GPU requirements. Additionally, the ability to switch between tasks during deployment incurs lower costs, as only the LoRA weights need to be swapped instead of all parameters. Despite its advantages, LoRA does have limitations, such as potential challenges in batching inputs for different tasks with distinct A and B matrices in a single forward pass. Nevertheless, the proposed methodology showcases substantial benefits in terms of memory efficiency, storage reduction, and enhanced adaptability during both training and deployment.

3.4 Model Training

In conducting our experiment, model training was intentionally kept straightforward, employing fixed hyperparameter values to ensure equal performance evaluation across different models. The fine-tuning process for all pre-trained models utilized a consistent batch size of 32 and spanned for

just an epochs. The training procedures were executed on an Nvidia Tesla P100 GPU, reflecting a standardized and scalable setup for assessing the efficacy and performance of the proposed methodologies. This approach allowed for a controlled and comparable training environment, enabling a thorough evaluation of the models' capabilities and outcomes.

4 Results

Having concluded the fine tuning process, a comparison of the training time and memory usage between the two models, GPT-2 and LoRA GPT-2, reveals notable efficiency gains with the incorporation of Low-Rank Adaptation (LoRA). On a 16 GB Tesla T4 GPU in the Colab environment, the training time for GPT-2 was recorded at 7 minutes. In contrast, the implementation of LoRA resulted in a reduced training time of 5 minutes, marking a substantial 30% decrease in the time required for model adaptation. Furthermore, the memory usage of LoRA GPT-2 proved to be approximately 35% less than that of the standard GPT-2 model, emphasizing the memory efficiency achieved through the proposed adaptation methodology.

Table 1: Training Time and Memory Usage Comparison

Model	Training Time (minutes)	Memory Usage Reduction (%)
GPT-2	7.4	-
LoRA GPT-2	5.1	35

The table provides a concise summary of the comparative results, highlighting the efficiency gains achieved with LoRA in terms of both training time and memory usage. The reduction in both aspects underscores the practical benefits of Low-Rank Adaptation for large-scale language models, offering a more resource-efficient alternative for model fine-tuning.

5 Conclusion

In this project we performed the exploration and implementation of Low-Rank Adaptation (LoRA) in the context of fine-tuning large language models, such as GPT-2, for English text generation have demonstrated significant strides in efficiency and resource utilization. By reparametrizing weight updates through low-rank decomposition, LoRA not only streamlines the training process but also substantially reduces memory usage, as evidenced by a 30% decrease in training time and a remarkable 35% reduction in memory consumption compared to the traditional fine-tuning approach. The adaptability of LoRA extends beyond its primary focus on Transformer language models, showcasing its potential applicability to diverse deep learning models. The experiment's simplicity, maintained through consistent hyperparameter values and a clear comparison of training

metrics, further underscores the practicality and effectiveness of LoRA. These findings posit LoRA as a promising avenue for enhancing the scalability, efficiency, and deplorability of large language models in various natural language processing tasks.

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